

Standard Operating Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers

Emitter	CARS & ARES
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Applicability of the document

These procedures apply to the ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing National Facilities and to the AERONET-ACTRIS associated photometer stations.

Acronyms

ACTRIS - Aerosol, Clouds and Trace gases Research InfraStructure

NF - National Facility

CARS - Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing

DC – Data Centre

MP – Mobile Platform

OP – Observational Platform

PI – Principal Investigator

ASP – Automatic Sun/sky/lunar Photometer

Reference documents

- [1]. Labelling of the ACTRIS National Facilities operating Aerosol Remote Sensing instruments
- [2]. Guidelines for EARLINET-ACTRIS associated stations to access QA services
- [3]. Technical requirements for ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms
- [4]. Technical requirements for ACTRIS Mobile Platforms operating automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
- [5]. Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
- [6]. ACTRIS CIMEL Photometer Guide for Users

Introduction

Detailed instructions are provided for the deployment, operation, quality control, and calibration of **CIMEL photometers** within the **AERONET-ACTRIS network**, for both **stationary** and **mobile/marine sites**. Through **rigorous facility-based calibration, weekly local and remote QC, and network-level verification**, every CIMEL CE318T photometer remains a reliable and accurate instrument for climate research, atmospheric monitoring, and environmental policy applications. This Guide summarizes the main relevant information all users / instruments PI must be aware of.

Integrating a CIMEL photometer into the ACTRIS–AERONET network begins with selecting a site that meets the network’s strict standards for atmospheric observations. Before deployment, the instrument must hold a valid **ACTRIS calibration certificate** issued by one of the network’s official Sun–Sky–Moon Photometer Calibration Units: **ASP-CNRS in France** or **ASP-UVA in Spain**. This guarantees that measurements are traceable to the network’s reference standards.

1 Instrument Overview

A CIMEL photometer is composed of three main components: the **optical head**, the **robotic unit**, and the **control unit** (Fig. 1). The optical head, which houses the collimator and the photodetectors, is connected to the control unit via the head cable, enabling bidirectional communication. A filter wheel is located in the sensor head with different interference filters: nine spectral bands from ultraviolet to near infrared (340, 380, 440, 500, 675, 870, 940, 1020 and 1640 nm) in the case of standard photometers. The robotic unit allows precise angular positioning for sun, sky or lunar scans. For stationary deployments, the control unit, batteries, and other electronics are housed in a waterproof box installed below the photometer, with solar panels positioned nearby to provide continuous power.

Figure 1: Parts of a CIMEL CE318 photometer.

2 Installation and Setup

1. Select a site free from obstructions, shadows, and reflective surfaces.
2. Securely mount the optical head and robotic unit on a stable platform.
3. Connect the optical head to the control unit via the head cable.
4. Position the waterproof box containing the control unit and batteries beneath the photometer. Ensure solar panels are oriented to maximize sunlight exposure.
5. Power up the system and verify initial communication between the control unit and optical head.

3 Data Acquisition and Transmission

- Use Photogetdata software to configure measurement schedules and acquire data.
- For stationary sites, ensure daily sun and sky measurements; lunar measurements are optional but recommended for night-time AOD retrieval.
- For mobile or marine operations, follow the mission-specific schedule and account for platform movement.
- Near-Real-Time transmits k8 files to the processing center to maintain continuous integration into the ACTRIS database and associated services.

4 Routine Checks and Maintenance

- Inspect optical head cleanliness, mechanical alignment, and robot operation.
- Verify the waterproof box and battery status; ensure solar panels are clean and unobstructed.
- Perform weekly checks, including system diagnostics, to detect any early signs of drift or malfunction (see Table 1).

Table 1: Weekly checks for CIMEL CE318T.

Set Manual mode
Remove head from robot
Check collimator and clean it if necessary with dry air. Observe the sky through the collimator to detect any obstruction (Fig. 2)
Check and clean lenses (only dry air, and only under indication of the calibration centers (Fig. 3)
Clean four quadrant sensor (Fig. 4)
Install head on robot
Check and clean the wetness sensor
Check date and time in the control box. If date is wrong or time is shifted more than 10 seconds from UTC time: Verify GPS cable is well connected and revise GPS info (Cimel Menu). If not, adjust control box to the right UTC time and contact manufacturer.
Check Pointing: Park, Gosun, Track, Park, Autorun. If pointing abnormal: check and correct robot levelling
Clean solar panels
Verify CIMEL to be running with: auto ON, MOON ON, turbo...

Figure 2: Detect (Left) and clean the collimator (right) of a CIMEL CE318T photometer

Figure 3: Clean lenses of a CIMEL CE318T photometer.

Figure 4: Clean the four quadrant sensor of a CIMEL CE318T photometer.

5 Additional resources

Goloub et al., Good practices : [a report on the requirements for SI-traceable calibrations of sunphotometers from aerosol remote sensing monitoring networks. Metrology for Aerosol Optical Properties.](#), 2023

*Giles, D. M., Sinyuk, A., Sorokin, M. G., Schafer, J. S., Smirnov, A., Slutsker, I., Eck, T. F., Holben, B. N., Lewis, J. R., Campbell, J. R., Welton, E. J., Korkin, S. V., and Lyapustin, A. I. (2019): Advancements in the Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) Version 3 database – automated near-real-time quality control algorithm with improved cloud screening for Sun photometer aerosol optical depth (AOD) measurements, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, **12**, 169-209, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-12-169-2019>.*